

CHARACTERISTICS OF IMPLEMENTATION OF TECHNICAL-TACTICAL ACTIONS DEPENDING ON THE METHOD OF CONDUCTING COMPETITIONS IN TYPES OF SPORTS WRESTLING

Solaydinov Elmurod Shoroidinovich

Theory and methodology of sports activities

Andijan state university

E-mail: elmurodshoroidinovich87@gmail.com

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Annotation: Most of the existing programs for the training of athletes in freestyle wrestling do not take into account the body-functional characteristics of the wrestlers during the various methods of conducting the competition, and these indicators are not only an accurate and reliable assessment of the wrestler's current condition, but also their reserve capabilities. allows prediction. The use of indicators that take into account the interaction of sports-technical actions with natural biological qualities allows wrestlers to compensate for their personal shortcomings.

Keywords: technique-tactics, skills, special sports training, wrestler, competition, combination method.

Аннотация: Большинство существующих программ подготовки спортсменов по вольной борьбе не учитывают телесно-функциональные особенности борцов при различных способах проведения соревнований, и эти показатели являются не только точной и достоверной оценкой текущего состояния борца. состояние, но и их резервные возможности позволяют прогнозировать. Использование показателей, учитывающих взаимодействие спортивно-технических действий с природными биологическими качествами, позволяет борцам компенсировать свои личностные недостатки.

Ключевая слова: техника-тактика, мастерство, специальная спортивная подготовка, борец, соревнование, комбинированный метод.

RESULTS AND ANALYSES

A wrestler's technical and tactical skill is considered an informative indicator of their specialized sports training. The author, Zamyatin Yu.P., approached the solution of the analyzed problem in a more traditional manner and defined the individual method of a wrestler's competitive activity as follows: "A system of behavioral techniques that determine the best results of activity when creating an optimal manner of conducting a wrestling match, oriented towards maximally utilizing the wrestler's strengths and qualities while compensating for their weaknesses."

At the same time, the author identifies the particular importance of signature techniques in technical and tactical actions, which are a crucial element in forming an individual wrestling style and are present in the wrestler's arsenal. The main conditions for improving signature techniques are the continuous expansion of the arsenal of ongoing technical and tactical actions and the constant search for the most effective tactical preparation options that contribute to the successful execution of these signature techniques. According to the authors, the process of individualizing the development of signature technical and tactical actions forms the basis of the content and structure of individual

training for freestyle wrestlers, with adequate consideration of the athletes' morphological data being an important component in such development.

The author has proposed and tested an experimental methodology for forming and purposefully improving the main technical and tactical actions. This methodology is implemented in three stages, with its characteristic tasks and means, methods, and methodology for solving them.

In martial arts, optimizing the training process often involves organizing the athlete's training activities in such a way that the specific features of the means, methods, and forms used in training, the improvement of combat tactics, and the creation of favorable conditions for performing technical and tactical actions are of great importance.

It is known that there are different methods of conducting competitions in wrestling. The author provides a more systematic representation of the main points of his concept, emphasizing that "when improving and correcting the individual method of activity that contributes to the successful performance of effective actions and competitive procedures by wrestlers, the main focus is on developing an individual program for conducting competitions." Such a program should ensure the most complete utilization of the natural characteristics and abilities of the nervous system of the individual, while simultaneously compensating for biological and personal shortcomings. At the same time, the author emphasizes that for wrestlers with a relatively strong nervous system, sharp-attacking and suppressive methods of conducting fights are more convenient than the same-type and straight-line method. For wrestlers with a relatively weak nervous system, it is more characteristic to conduct fights using various technical and tactical means in a game-based, combinational manner. These two opposing groups of wrestlers do not encompass all the diversity of individual characteristics and their manifestation during competitive contests, and they have significant differences in the arsenal and effectiveness of technical and tactical actions. This depends on psychophysiological conditions and should be taken into account when training highly qualified wrestlers.

A high level of technical and tactical mastery is based on the combined method of conducting competitions, that is, an integral indicator of special sports training. Combinational wrestling is recognized as the most modern form of its manifestation, ensuring a high level of audience interest. For example, according to the author, combative struggle ensures the solution of the following tasks: 1) dominance of offensive actions; 2) the pursuit of a goal that is accompanied by a high potential for action; 3) possessing positional initiative; 4) Development of optimal instructions for the entire process of conducting competitive competitions.

A group of researchers proposed dividing highly qualified wrestlers into three types depending on their motor characteristics - technical, strength, and functional characteristics. At the same time, wrestlers of technical manners are characterized by a significantly larger arsenal of highly evaluated technical and tactical actions, while athletes of functional and strength types are characterized by a significantly limited arsenal of techniques with a less effective evaluation. The improvement of strengths and elimination of shortcomings in all group wrestlers should be carried out at all stages of training, with the selection of specific means and methods taking into account the individual characteristics of the athletes.

Analysis of the methods of forming an individual method of wrestlers' activities confirmed that the main aspects of the method are determined by the typological features of

the nervous system during the relative influence of a number of external factors. At the same time, the author notes that in order to adequately develop such a method, it is necessary to thoroughly study the typological features of the wrestler's nervous system. The authors noted that highly skilled wrestlers differ significantly in the strength of their nervous processes and belong to different typological groups, with very characteristic features in solving technical and tactical tasks. It is recommended to form the technical arsenal of wrestlers and methods for its implementation by taking into account the individual characteristics of athletes in accordance with the individual method of competitive activity.

By dividing athletes into three groups according to their individual orientation in implementing technical and tactical skills during competitive competitions, the specifics of the skills of wrestlers of different tactical styles in conducting competitions have been determined. From a technical and tactical standpoint, "player" wrestlers who prioritize superiority and use strength resistance are distinguished; "speed" wrestlers who gain victory in the competition due to high speed. At the same time, it cannot be denied that there are individual wrestlers who conduct the competition in a "universal" manner, possessing qualities belonging to each of the listed types. By studying athletes with high sports proficiency, two most typical groups of wrestlers (conducting fights using low-intensity or high-intensity methods) were identified, which, according to the authors, allows for a high level of individualization of the training process. At the same time, the author has developed individual-group training programs for improving the technical and tactical skills of the listed wrestlers.

The substantive basis for creating combinations is the attack, defense, counter-methods, and bundles used in various variations. Combinational wrestling deepens knowledge of all situations that arise during wrestling. The combined wrestling style sharpens training throughout the entire athletic career, both at the training and competitive stages. Therefore, great importance is attached to the improvement of technical and tactical training in a combinatorial direction. Leading coaches systematically seek rational ways, means, and methods for enhancing the professional sports skills of their students. The content of modern sports wrestling is constantly being improved, and the athletes' motor potential is enriched with new methods of defense, combinations, and bundles. An athlete who has mastered combinational wrestling has the ability to quickly transition from one method to another. The attacking athlete has a real advantage over his opponent, as defense against successive combined series that are logically interconnected is more difficult than defense against a single method. The opponent is forced to react twice in his defensive reaction against the attacking wrestler's planned combination action, which leads to a delay in the response to the second attack. This ensures the attacking wrestler's success in completing the final method. A special study was conducted to study the combinational techniques of elite wrestlers worldwide and identify structural combinations for creating effective combinations in sports wrestling.

The combinations depicted are complex offensive actions. In combinational wrestling, the use of techniques related to leg impact on the opponent's legs allows for the intensification of the offensive effect and the faster achievement of pure victory. The resulting effect of a bilateral impact, performed simultaneously with the arms and legs, creates the necessary conditions for the opponent to lose balance. In this case, against the backdrop of losing a

stable balance, the opponent must concentrate on controlling the attacking wrestler's two-way movement. The loss of balance by the opponent is also ensured by tactical preparation performed before the attack. The combined method of conducting competitions is based on the interaction between preparatory actions and defensive or counterattacking actions of the opponent. The combination of methods has a significant advantage over individual methods. This means that the opponent tries to perform a strong defense from the first attack without doubting the complexity of the attack and does not have time to react to the final combination method with the next defense.

An analytical approach to analyzing the technical content of combinations in a standing position allowed for the determination of their structure: 1) attack - defense - attack; 2) attack - defense - counterattack - counterattack; 3) attack - counterattack - defense - attack. In the parter, the priority is: 1) counterattack - defense - counterattack; 2) counterattack - defense - attack. We have established that the following actions of the attacking wrestler are based on the structural structures of the combinations: 1) tactical training methods (TTP), jerks, pushes; 2) Rapid displacement of the center of gravity of its body; 3) tangential and rapidly changing grasps and repeated grasps; 4) maneuvering; 5) deceptive attack methods; 6) defences (performed by an opponent); 7) Complete attack methods. The grasps performed by the attacking wrestler can be divided into preliminary and main.

In some cases, combinations are performed from beginning to end without changing the grip (permanent grip). Complex coordination and technical actions in sports wrestling cannot be used in full by a person with a significantly larger arsenal. This is due to the fact that the psychological and stressful conditions of the wrestling competition make it difficult to choose an adequate action for situations that change instantly. It is precisely this factor that forces coaches to speak about the feasibility of forming the king method. According to the author, the following motto should be dominant during training in sports wrestling (as in other types of martial arts): "Winning with minimal technical actions during the maximum possible situations in combat." According to the author, the development of the ability to perceive the nature of training and competitive loads, to react to them optimally, and to adequately measure physical and spiritual strength with them is an important and extremely complex problem of improving young kurash athletes in sports. If this problem can be successfully solved in the process of competitive and pre-competitive training for older athletes, then it is necessary to prioritize the cultivation of these qualities in the conditions of training for adolescent kurash wrestlers. The level of competitive activity in sports wrestling requires highly effective skills in performing complex attacking movements from wrestlers, which implies the sequential application of several instantaneous positional attacking techniques at a single attacking impulse. In this case, the opponent loses to the attacker in terms of reaction time. Wrestlers who use are more likely to win competitions, and their style of conducting competitions is significant in terms of spectacularness. However, during the training process, there are still problems with the training process. However, the formation of technical skills often occurs through attempts and errors, as there is no single scientifically sound methodology for training, taking into account the individual characteristics of athletes.

CONCLUSION

Most scientific publications should focus on improving the technical and tactical actions of kurash wrestlers. However, conducting competitions according to new rules requires not only a significant amount of physical exertion from wrestlers, but also psychological exertion,

which ultimately leads to a lack of strength and a decrease in reserve capabilities. Many existing programs for training freestyle wrestlers do not take into account the body and functional characteristics of wrestlers during different styles of wrestling, and these indicators allow for an accurate and reliable assessment of the wrestler's current state, as well as a prediction of their reserve capabilities. The application of indicators taking into account the interaction of sports and technical actions with natural biological qualities allows for the compensation of personal shortcomings of kurash wrestlers, which has not yet been studied in detail.

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